

The Temple Village of Maluti: A Re-appraisal of Bengali Identity and Culture from the Margin

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Abstract

While defining the Bengali identity and culture, most of the people often simplify it and, in their replies, we find some recurrent terms, like, “Maachh Bhaat” (fish with boiled rice), “Robi Thakur”, “Durga Puja” and “Rosogolla”. But, is the Bengali identity only limited to these terms! Well, those above-mentioned terms do represent some facets of Bengali culture, but limiting the entire culture within those terms, simplifying the identity is basically diminishing the complex Bengali culture and making the other facets of culture obsolete. For understanding the culture, we can take example of the little hamlet, Maluti, which is literally at the margin or border of Bengal and Jharkhand. For many years this village has suffered from lack of government attention after independence. While the nearby villages and towns were enjoying the products of electricity, this village was shunned to primitive darkness. It is only in the first decade of 21st century that they have seen the flash of electricity. But in earlier years the village has seen much prosperous days. With the help of Mr. Gopaldas Mukherjee, a local teacher and an independent researcher who has reached his 90s, I have come across the fact that, with the break of 16th century, the then densely forested stony land observed the emergence of a new kingdom, The Nankar Kingdom (tax-free kingdom). As a reward for rescuing the pet hawk of Sultan Allaudin Hussain Shah of Gaur, a twelve-year-old orphan Brahmin boy Basanta Roy received this tax-free land, consisting of villages like, Damra (first capital), Maluti (final capital), Masra, Kashthagara, Hastikanda, Katigram, Surichua etc. In this kingdom we see a Vajrayana Buddhist shrine of Amitabha and his power deity Prajna Pandarvini converted into a Hindu Shakta temple of Maa Mouliksha in the hands of a clan of Shamkara Vedantists. We find a king who even though being a Shakta, built 108 Terracotta temples of Shiva. With the emergence of people from Vaishnava faith, we find Vishnu temples and Kali temple made in the format of Rasamancha of Krishna. Even the terracotta arts on the temples show figures from Bhagavada Purana and also the Durga of Shakta faith in the same building. We can see Santali tribe performing during the Kali puja. We can even find documents of Princess Kashishwari Devi donating tax-free lands to the Muslim community to build Majahar for Kalapir. When we pay attention to the centre only, the identity of the Bengali people may be reduced to Maach-Bhaat, Robi Thakur, Durga Pujo and Rosogolla and those who are in power successfully cash on these simplified versions. The plurality in Bengali culture, the complexities it has acquired over ages are often denied. Maluti, known as Gupta Kashi (Secret Varanasi) in the times of the Sunga rulers in Bengal is absent in the cultural map of the Bengalis. But like the ghost of Hamlet’s father this absence haunts. In this paper I wish to capture that Derridian “hauntology” with reference to Maluti, a place associated with the hallowed presence of Sadhak Bama Khyapa.

Introduction

While defining the Bengali identity and culture some people often simplify it and reduce all sorts of complexities into specific markers like “Maachh Bhaat” (fish with boiled rice), “Robi Thakur”, “Durga Puja” and “Rasogolla”. There is hardly any doubt that the above-mentioned markers do represent some facets of Bengaliness. But limiting the entire culture to those terms, and simplifying its complexity does not actually do any justice. Bengali culture and identity are not so simple.

In this paper, I would try to understand Bengali culture and identity by taking examples of and from the little hamlet, Maluti which is literally situated at the margin or border of West Bengal and at the neighbouring state of Jharkhand. For many years since independence, this village has suffered from lack of government attention. While the nearby villages and towns were enjoying the benefits of electricity, this village particularly was shunned to primitive darkness. It is only in the first decade of the 21st century that the villagers saw electric light. However, till date they face numerous power-cuts throughout a day!

Interestingly however, the face of the village was not so dark in the remote past. Instead of being reckoned as one of the deprived villages located at a geographically marginalized position and almost absent from the cultural cartography of the Bengali people, in the olden days its position was quite central in the context of Bengali culture and identity. With the help of Mr. Gopaldas Mukherjee, ex-military personnel, and also a local teacher and an independent researcher who has just reached his 90s, I have come across the fact that with the break of the 16th century, the then densely forested stony land observed the emergence of a new kingdom, the Nankar Kingdom (tax-free kingdom) which had been given as a reward to a twelve year old Brahmin boy named Basanta Roy by Sultan Allaudin Hussain Shah of Gaur for rescuing his pet hawk. Basanta Roy received this land consisting of villages namely Damra (his first capital), Maluti (the final capital), Masra, Kashthagara, Hastikanda, Katigram, and Surichua (Mukherjee 19). Surendra Jha re-narrates the entire legend:

The Sultan of Bengal, Ala-ud-din Hussain Shah (1493 -1519) was returning from his Orissan campaigns to Jajnagar. The Sultan encamped on the banks of the river Mor or Mayurakshi [...] for a week. In the meantime a pet eagle of his queen Begum Mahal fled away with a golden chain [...] and] a golden earring too. The bird was so favourite for Begum Mahal that she insisted on getting it back and went on hunger strike to

press her demand before the Sultan. Therefore, the Sultan announced that whosoever will bring back the bird will get a reward as desired. [...] In the meantime, Svami Nigamananda Tirtha of Kashi Sumeru Matha was returning from a pilgrimage [...] When he reached near a village called Katigrama, he saw that a boy was sleeping under the shade of a tree in the grazing field and cobra was protecting his head from the scorching sun by spreading its hood. Nigamananda Tirtha was surprised to see it and guessed about the bright future of the boy. [...] As per calculation of Nigamananda, Basant Mukherjee had been given wrong mantra [by his guru] which delayed the process of his becoming a Raja. [...] Therefore, Nigamananda [...] initiated the process of [giving] Simhabahini Mantra. [...] The Svami [soon after] found that Basant had caught the eagle with golden ear ring and golden chain. The boy and the Svami then went to the camp of the Sultan. [...] The Svami, on behalf of Basant, asked for land. The Sultan ordered that the next day early in the morning Basant would ride a horse and all the land trodden by the horse and Basant till sunset would be allotted to him rent free. Basant covered [...] an area of 20 kos (40 miles). [...] He was given the title of Raja and a sword as well. From that day, he came to be known as Baj Basant Ray, the Raja of Nankar estate. (Jha, Surendra 27-28)

This is a fascinating story based on certain folkloric formula though there is no point in denying that it projects like many other historically important places in Bengal a glorious past during the rule of the Sultan.

The Absence Haunts

Gopal Das Mukherjee has further pointed out that in the past Maluti was known as Gupta Kashi (Secret Varanasi) (Mukherjee, Personal Interview). It provokes me to think about another very significant place in the cultural cartography of Bengal, another temple village Bishnupur located in the Bankura district which was known as Gupta Vrindavan (Secret Vrindavan). Bishnupur is very central in our imagination, its terracotta temples have phenomenal existence yet the fate of Maluti has not been so prosperous. In the times of the Sunga rulers the Gupta Kashi identity of this place was much celebrated. But as I had visited the place today and listened to its tale from Mr Gopal Das Mukherjee it appeared to me that not unlike the ghost of Hamlet's father its absence haunts the Bengali

culture and identity. I wish to read that absence with reference to Maluti, a place associated with the hallowed presence of the famous tantra practitioner Bama Khyapa. Hope it would not be unfair to refer to what Derrida says that even after the political end of communism with the fall of Soviet Russia, Marx would haunt the European minds as the ghost of Hamlet's father haunted the play (Derrida 10). According to Derrida one can neither prove the existence of the ghost nor deny it. It is quite similarly the absent-presence of Maluti in the cartography of culture and identity of the Bengali people haunts. In Derrida, the idea of "hauntology" challenges the idea of pre-existing homonymous term ontology of existence (Derrida 202). Apart from "Maachh Bhaat", "Robi Thakur", "Durga Puja" and "Rasogolla" – the centrality of a place like Bishnupur conjures from the past the apparition of Maluti which from its very insignificant and marginal existence these days seeks to subvert the position of the centre and the central. Mr Gopal Das Mukherjee would also agree to the point that in his village the ghost of the past makes its presence palpable so that the present is often shocked. How prosperous was Maluti originally and how is it today? I resorted to a reliable newspaper article for answer:

Deep in Jharkhand's hinterland lies the village of Maluti. Flanked by mud houses and a handful of concrete buildings, narrow lanes lead to several open spaces right in the middle of the village — spaces that bear testimony to more than 300 years of rich temple architecture. Once home to 108 temples, the village is now but a poor shadow of its past, with only 72 shrines remaining — but the sheer number puts Maluti on the heritage map of India. [...]

The temples, mostly of Shiva, are dotted in five different clusters — Sikir Taraf, Rajar Bari, Madhya Bari, Chhoi Taraf and the Mauliksha temple complex.

Situated in Dumka district, the village is close to the border with West Bengal, and Chala architecture, inspired by traditional Bengali huts with their sloping roofs with curved edges, is a distinct feature of Maluti's temples. Also, the influence of the exquisite Keshta Raya terracotta temple at Bishnupur in Bengal's Bankura district can be seen clearly in every temple. The 17th century masonry technique using moulded bricks has been applied extensively.

(The Hindu: <https://www.thehindu.com/society/history-and-culture/the-terracotta-temples-of-maluti/article30642993.ece>)

It makes amply clear that once a flourished Bengali establishment Maluti has now lost its glory with rolling times and the once a cultural centre of *Rahr* Bengal it has been relegated to the margin to become the ghost of its past existence.

Going back to Derrida I must reiterate, when one comes face to face with the past and watches the densely situated terracotta temples of Maluti, the absence of the glories of the bygone days haunts us, though we cannot merely deny its presence. The village is not even located within the political territory of West Bengal and still even in its fragile condition shocks like the apparition of Banquo. It compels me to pay heed to it, study it carefully and acknowledge the complex cultural identity of Bengal as represented beautifully in terms of plurality.

Existing Heritage of Maluti

Hence it was with the help of Mr. Gopal Das Mukherjee, the lone flag-bearer I came across the rich cultural heritage of this village. Due to his two decades long research over Maluti's cultural heritage, the village has recently come into government focus and restoration works are also taking place. But even then, an irreparable onslaught of time has taken its course over the heritage of Maluti. As already to some extent pointed out in the aforementioned newspaper article and I also extensively surveyed during fieldwork, the remains of total 108 terracotta temples can be found in that little village of only 406 hectares or 4.06 sq.km. This is no surprise that it has much greater density than that of Bishnupur in the district of Bankura (392 sq.km.). But now only 72-75 temples are in existence.

(Ruined terracotta temples)

It is believed by Mr Gopal Das Mukherjee that the village was once under the rule of the Malla kings of Bankura, and thus one can find a striking similarity among the temples of the two places. But Surendra Jha points out in this context:

It is said that in the medieval period it was a part of Mallahattii raj bordering on Damin-i-Koh of Santal Parganas, Burdwan, Midnapur and West Chotanagpur. Adi Malla was the first ruler and Bir Hambheer was the last ruler of this dynasty bearing the title of Malla. Afterwards they adopted Ksatriya title 'Singh' and their territory was known as Bishnupur Raj [...]

[But]The Mallabhuma of Malla Rajas correspond to the present district of Bankura which is to the south of the district of Burdwan at a reasonable distance.

Moreover, Malla chiefs were small zamindars who must not have held suzerainty to such a distant place like Maluti.

The settlement report of the district of Birbhum mentions Mallarpur, (a railway station on Eastern Railway Loopline) which is near Maluti and Tara Pitha as center of Malla Kingdom. But this confusion has arisen due to similarity of name. There was one Mallar Singh who had come from the west. He was one of the many Rajputs who migrated to the eastern Province in the wake of Muslim invasions. Mallar Singh founded the village which is presently known as Mallarpur. He was counted as a Zamindar of Birbhum and not as the vassal of Bishnupur Raj. Therefore [revision was done on the] old opinion that the village was a part of Bankura Malla Kingdom. (Jha, Surendra. 20 -21)

Nevertheless, such differences of opinion do not stop from repeating the fact that there has been much similarity between the temples of Bishnupur and the temples at Maluti.

It is quite a curious thing to notice that even though they enjoyed a tax-free land the rulers of Nankar Maluti never indulged into making a palace for their own, and lived in ordinary mud houses like the other inhabitants of the village. As the land was stony in nature and people had to suffer from water crisis, it was throughout their reign they dug many water bodies. They helped develop a prosperous village by bringing in people from various places and giving them lands to cultivate. And apart from this they hugely contributed to the cultural enrichment of the place. Building the temples, they did this last

thing most impressively. About the most noted architectural features of the temples are the story-telling terracotta plaques about which it has been pointed out:

The terracotta plaques were neither carved on the walls nor were they like stuccos; rather, they stuck on using *vajralepa*. This is a paste prepared by mixing local sand, betel nut, horsehair, coconut fibre, brick powder, molasses, a stringent made of *Aegle marmelos* trees and oil gum resin beeswax, and allowing the mix to decompose.

(<https://www.thehindu.com/society/history-and-culture/the-terracotta-temples-of-maluti/article30642993.ece>)

After so many centuries these plaques are intact and have been telling various mythological tales to people of the time past, present and to come.

Sometimes a pertinent question arises: why so many temples at a place? With the aid of Mr. Gopal Das Mukherjee, we come across a funny answer that some temples were made initially due to the order from the king's *Kulguru*, but in much later times it became a matter of competition among the four brothers of the royal family and as a result we find such a rich built heritage.

A very central temple in the village in terms of its significance is that of the village goddess and the *Kul Devi* of the rulers, Maa Mouliksha (literal meaning "face-only goddess"). Surendra Jha gives a detailed description of this temple which must be quoted here:

The temple of Mauliksha is also a Do Chala Temple with a front porch or verandah, which is comparatively rare.

The sanctum or Garbha – grha of the temple is 8'6" long and 5'2" wide in which the idol is placed in the middle. The veranda of the temple or the front porch is 9'4"x4'0" respectively in length and wide. There is a window in the garbh-griha on the left side which is 1'3" wide having a rectangular height of 1'6" over which there is an arch having a radius of 0.7.5" (seven point five inches). The door of the temple is 2' wide and 4' high over which there is an arch having a radius of one foot. The height of the garbhagrha is 9' 10" in which 8' 6" is the vertical height and the rest 1'4" goes to make the two-sided scope of the chala.

The front porch of the temple (9'4"x 4' 0") has three openings of 2' x 4 ½" over which there are arches having 1' radius. The porch of verandah has small circular pillars (with round base) encarcinated by semi-cylindrical

projections heightened by arched openings. There is a newly built verandah which is open on all sides. The dimension of the verandah is 35'x24'x12'. In this hall-cum-verandah, there are four pillars on the left side (north) and four pillars on right side (south). [...] The hall-verandah is flat roofed with gentle slopings but the front view is triangular over which there is Padma (Lotus), Kalsa (water-jar) and Trident (Trisula). [...] The campus of the Mauliksha temple is – W 112'.0'' x S 110'.0''x E 116'.5''x N 102'.8''. Thus the campus is free from the Surya – Vedha as prescribed in *Vastu Sastra* because the width from the Northern wall to Southern wall (i.e. 112'.0'' and 116'.5'') is greater than the width from Western Wall to Eastern Wall (i.e. 110'.0''x 103'.8''). The front gate of Mauliksha temple is 5' wide. There is a back door in the campus on eastern side which is 3' wide. In the North East corner, there is a small kitchen for preparation of *Bhoga* on the western side near the front gate, there is a Siva Temple which is the oldest among the Siva temples of Maluti. (Jha, Surendra 94-99)

The interesting fact about the goddess is that it has been there even before the establishment of the kingdom in that region. It was a seat of Amitabha-asana of the Vajrayana Buddhists and their deity Prajna Pandaravasini, and the idol of goddess Pandara is worshipped as Mauliksha. It is said that the goddess was found by the Kulguru Dandi Swami of Sumeru Math of Kashi in ruins and he started worshipping her as Maa Mouliksha (Mukherjee 93-94). An important fact is that the Sumeru Math is responsible for transforming numerous Buddhist shrines into Hindu temples. Thus, this apparently innocent event could be part of a bigger propaganda in the olden days. Surendra Jha also admits the presence of the Vajrayana in this region:

The region was a centre of Vajrayana Buddhism as evidenced by archeological, epigraphical and literary proofs. The Chinese account of Hiuen-Tsang refers to many Mahayanist Buddhist temples in Kajangala (Rajmahal), Pundra-Vardhana (North Bengal), Samatata (South East Bengal), Tamralipti (Midnapore), Karnasuvarna (Murshidabad). The region of Anga, Banga and Sumha had been the centres of non – Brahminical cults particularly of Buddhism. During the rule of Pala Kings, the Buddhism took the form of several yans of which Vajrayana was the most important. After the decline of Pala empire and consequent fall of the

monastery of Vikramsila (near Kahalgaon in Bhagalpur district of Bihar), which was the citadel of Vajrayanists; there is every likelihood that persecuted by Muslim invaders from the period of Bakhtiyar Khalji, the Buddhist monks might have taken shelter in adjacent hilly and forested areas inaccessible to the invaders. And as we know, Maluti and its surroundings were one of such areas. (Jha, Surendra 23-24)

In addition to this observation, Jha has also pointed out that moving from Maluti to Shikaripara block headquarters one would find along the banks of the Brahmani river various relics related to Vajrayana. For example, at a place called Panchavahini a “Manipadma Chakra having forty petals is found. [...] Another Padma – chakra of eleven petals is also found. A Padma – Yoni chakra has been found with a yantra engraved on stone. There is an inscription as well in Proto Bangla script mentioning Tara.” He is indeed right in surmising with many other scholars that in the 14th and 15th centuries Maluti was the centre of the Vajrayanis. But at the same time Jha does not agree with Mr. Gopal Das Mukherjee on the point that Maa Mouliksha is in fact Pandara. He notes:

We finally conclude that Devi Mauliksha was conceived as Rakta Tara or Tripurasundari and Lalita of Sankaracharya’s version of Saktism known as Samayacara. [...] In course of time, we find that Bamdeva Chattopadhyaya (Bama Khepa) the famous Sadhaka of Tara Pitha, had his early practice at Maluti in the temple of Mauliksha which also makes the above identification quite clear. [...] the period in which Raja Rakharh Chandra Ray consecrated the image of Mauliksha, i.e. the last quarter of the 17th century the influence of Buddhist Vajrayana had been completely eradicated and Buddhist saktis. e.g. Pandara, Mamaki etc. had been completely absorbed as avarana-Devis attendant on Tara. [...] Conclusively we may say that Maluti was the Vajrayani centre before the foundation of Maluti when it was full of jungles. The site was abandoned by the Vajrayanists and the image of Mauliksha, which might have been worshipped as the Arya Tara of Vajrayana, was buried beneath the earth. When it was discovered by Raja Rakharh Chandra Ray, he consecrated the goddess as worshipped from old days buried beneath the earth. [...] later on, Raja [...] invoked Tara (the second Maha Vidya of Sakta Tantra) in the image of Mauliksha. Thus, the presiding goddess of Maluti-Mauliksha is

the rare, synthesis of Vajrayana, Saiva and Sakta Tantra cults. (Jha, Surendra 61)

Nevertheless, this may also not to be accepted without further probe into this subject.

Hence after finding out the fact that Maa Mouliksha of Maluti could actually be Vajrayana Buddhist goddess, I enquired about the origin and practices surrounded specifically with the goddess Pandara. And with further reading I knew that it was customary with the Vajrayana Buddhist to establish idols of Devi Prajna Pandaravasini and her male counterpart Amitabha Buddha together. But no existence of Amitabha Buddha is known to the villagers of Maluti. Only the goddess Pandara exists in the form of Maa Mouliksha. We cannot forget the fact that the goddess was first discovered by Dandi Swami of Sumeru Math, a Shankar Vedantist, a disciple of Acharya Shankara who once took the campaign of purging India of Buddhism through a non-violent way of debating and appropriating. Although, we often find Buddha as the ninth avatar of Lord Vishnu in Vaishnava Hinduism (even though Buddha himself denied the hierarchy of Vedic culture and propounded a *Nastika* or heterodox school), no temple built under the influence of Shankar Vedantists depict Buddha as the ninth reincarnation. This seems as a deliberate attempt of omitting the memory of the Buddha and his cult. Could it be that Maluti too came under the same process of purgation and appropriation?

Nevertheless, I find two stone blocks curved as lotuses and seem as if forming a base for a 5-6 ft. long statue. The statue is missing and everyone can remember only the stone blocks located there in the Mouliksha temple complex.

(Lotus like stone pedestal for a missing statue)

A notable fact is that Lotus is the specific symbol of Amitabha Buddha. We can also find some broken black-stone statues, which are not at all identifiable. According to Mr. Gopal Das Mukherjee those statues are of the time of the Pala dynasty of Bengal, an era when Vajrayana Buddhism flourished the most. Thus, I come up with two possible reasons for the absence of Amitabha Buddha in Maluti. Either the Buddha statue was broken in the process of making the goddess Pandara as a Hindu goddess named Maa Mouliksha or, it was already destroyed by some invasion before its discovery by Dandi Swami, as the place is said to have been abandoned by the Abadhoots and when Dandi Swami found the temple it was already in ruins.

Just to add to more on cultural complexities, I find another curious fact among the terracotta temples of Maluti when a Kali temple is seen built in the model of Vaishnava Rasmancha.

(Kali Temple made in the model of Rasmancha)

How excellent a manner has this been of the fusion of two different cults of opposing ideologies! It is indeed a great pleasure to listen to some of our *Shakta* poets of the nineteenth and twentieth century Bengal, especially Kolkata composing lyrics that tell of such fusion. Far away from the modern cultural centre where heads of ideologies were transposed due to highly powerful socio-economic factors related with modernity Maluti's temple is an example to reckon with separately.

As I look intently at the terracotta panels of the temples of this half-forgotten village, I also find the incredible mixture of the sacred and the profane. On one panel, for example Krishna's *Bakashura Badh* is portrayed and on the other a *Babu* saunters under the parasol hold by his loyal servant.

(Plaques depicting the *Bakasura Badh* and Servant holding umbrella over a Babu, respectively)

Both the images are present in the same row. It means the panel speaks for a culture which holds together narratives from the *Vaishnava Purana* and as well as depictions from the eighteenth-century Bengali society and culture. In the hands of rural yet highly skilled Bengali artisans from *Rahr* the deities are represented in some Bengali versions of their own. There are hardly any difference between men – women and gods-goddesses here; all the terracotta panels portray the deities as human beings, especially as Bengalis, as it has been done to Lord Shiva and goddess Durga in Bengali *Gajan* where in folksongs dedicated to them Shiva becomes a Bengali farmer “Shibai” and Durga his typical Bengali wife.

To add some more spice to this variety, I must recount my observation of a Muslim shrine of Pir Kalasaheb at the nearby village. It is believed that the land for this shrine was contributed by Princess Kashiswari Devi of Maluti (Mukherjee 103). Here I had found a very unique aspect of cultural mixture when it came to the use of vermilion or *Sindur*, which could not generally be found in Islam. Yet another noticeable example of communal integrity can be seen in a specially built Shiva temple, where the complex comprising of three temples made in the model of a temple, a mosque and a church respectively.

(Trio Shiva Temple in the format of Temple-Masjid-Church)

The second temple in between the temple and church is made in the model of a mosque which is a result of being under the protection of a Muslim Sultan, and the existence of a church also depicts the prominence gained in much later times by the East India Company in Bengali society. Thus, the entire village is a text of plurality and integrity, not merely something to be known through any simplified cultural marker.

Not only in the field of sculpture and architecture, the Nankar kingdom of Maluti ventured into the field of literature also. During the reign of King Anandachandra of Nankar Maluti, a poet named Ganga Narayan Mukhoti (Mukherjee) from the neighbouring village to Maluti, Hastikanda wrote *Bhavani Mangal*, which is now safely preserved in the archive of Visva Bharati, the Central University (Mukherjee 61). Raigunakar Bharatchandra Roy wrote *Annada Mangal* in the court of King Krishnachandra of Krishnanagar. According to Mr. Gopal Das Mukherjee, the poet of *Bhavani Mangal* Ganga Narayan Mukhoti was a distant cousin of Bharatchandra, and both of them were descendants of Krittibas Ojha, the famous author of the well-known Bengali *Ramayana* (62). As Bharatchandra was bestowed with the title ‘Raigunakar’, Ganga Narayan Mukhoti was also honoured with the title ‘Chakladar’. He was subsequently offered the village Hastikanda as a tax-free land by King Anandachandra of Maluti for writing *Bhavani Mangal*. The two literary pieces namely *Annadamangal* and *Bhavani Mangal* were written by the two cousins, Bharatchandra and Ganga Narayan respectively within the same period of time. Yet only *Annadamangal* by Raigunakar

Bharatchandra Roy is known as a pioneering literary text while the other remained almost unheard of to the Bengali ears. This may be called another example of marginalisation. The then centre of Bengali culture, the court of King Krishnachandra of Krishnanagar, its political prominence in the then political unrest due to the conflict between the Nawab and the East India Company, probably helped *Annadamangal* to come into prominence. In comparison Nankar kingdom was quite the under-dog, and as a result *Bhavani Mangal* remained in the darkness of ignorance.

However, after being aware of such shocking facts from the book *Nankar Maluti* by Mr. Gopaldas Mukherjee, I went on to verify the facts, and visited the village Hastikanda, where descendants of Ganga Narayan Mukhoti or Chakladar are still living. There I met with Mr. Shyama Prasad Chakladar, a Forest Ranger of Dabgram Forest Range, Siliguri, Darjeeling and Mr. Tapan Kr. Chakladar, a retired DSP, CID, Bhawani Bhawan, Kolkata. As representatives of the family, they confirmed the facts by showing a family tree showing their lineage from Krittibas Ojha. But they could not verify the relation between Ganga Narayan Chakladar and Raigunakar Bharatchandra Roy. However, Mr. Gopal Das Mukherjee has been kind enough to share some quoted lines from the *mukhabandha* or invocation and *Bhanita* or author's identity, to show the literary expertise of Ganga Narayan Mukhoti as presented in *Bhavani Mangal*.

Lines from the *Mukhabandha* or invocation-

Brahman kuler mani Sakal sabhate jini
Shrijuta Anandachandra Rai
Tar sabhasad kobi Chandir charan bhabi
Dwija Ganganarayan-e Gai (Mukherjee 62)

(Brahmin Ganga Narayan, who is the court-poet of Lord Anandachandra Rai, who is the gem of Brahmin clan and winner over all courts, sings.)

Lines from *bhanita* or author's identity-

Nibas Meteri gram Pitamaha Ramram
Tituram tahar nandan
Tar suta Ram nija Ganganarayan Dwija
Uma-geet korilo rachan (Mukherjee 62)

(Brahmin Ganga Narayan also known as Ram, son of Tituram, grandson of Ramram of village Meteri, writes the song of Uma or Durga.)

These lines vividly put forward some examples of literary genius that Nankar Maluti presented in the eighteenth century. Thus, it is very natural that whenever someone from

the centre comes face to face with the unheard literary masterpiece like *Bhavani Mangal*, it appears as a shock to that person. Dr. Panchanan Mondal, who probably collected and preserved the manuscript of *Bhavani Mangal* for the archives of Visva Bharati had probably realised the importance of the literary piece. But the authority or Dr. Panchanan Mondal himself put no effort to publish or make people aware of the existence of an unheard of *mangal kavya*.

Conclusion

Thus, we see that Maluti is an example, a living legend of many cultural phases and transformations occurred throughout Bengal over the ages. The entire village is a text of almost the entire history of Bengali culture and identity forgotten by Bengali people due to their excessive attention to the centre.

Throughout the ages this stony land has observed numerous cultural changes. Beginning with Vajrayana Buddhism, this land contained cultures with the philosophical views of Shaktism, Shaivism, Vaishnavism and then Muslim and Tribal cultures. Temples made in the form of Masjid, Church and Temple together in the same compound, Kali temple in the form of Rasmancha, vermilion used to worship a Muslim Pir are instances of such a diverse cultural co-habitation. Santhals, who have been a part and parcel of this entire village also finds the Kali Puja of this village as a festival of their own. It has been the same for centuries, that Santhals celebrating the Kali puja for seven days in their own way and doing Kali puja. The absence of this large chunk of cultural identity becomes very much palpable when we come face to face with this ghost from the past.

But what caused such a flourishing establishment to turn into a deserted village? When we visit this village, we can only find elderly people clinging to their hereditary homes, whereas, the young are scattered throughout the world. Therefore, none of them are really concerned about their own homeland. From an interview with Mr. Gopaldas Mukherjee I came to know that the main reason for such a condition is incapability to cope up with the rapidly changing world. People who used to live by their hereditary occupations in the village gradually found their occupations futile and started moving to nearby towns. Lack of government attention made them abandon their homelands and gradually forget about the glorious past. According to Mr. Mukherjee the only purpose for his research was to bring back the inhabitants of the village. And according to him the only way of reviving the village is boosting the tourism for the village. And to boost the tourism we need to take heed of the ghost and fill up the absence or gap in our cultural identity, caused by excessive attention to the centre and our effort of finding a singular definition to our cultural identity.

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